

Private Devotional Worlds

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Hope is the sign of a true Christian. If we are able to live our life in hope, we can also find joy though we walk through difficult times. Our life as a community, and our prayers and pious practices are to share our joys and pains, and make the encounter with God a living reality. Devotions use different things, postures, colours, tines, fragrance where by our touch of the sacred can be more sensible and meaningful. Something that is very important is the interaction through which our life receives new hope and strength.

Often there is a risk that the whole life and its value may be defined as being within a number of pious practices. We may be creating a devotional world for ourselves. We cannot practice Christian hope being in a private devotional world. Christ himself lived prayerfully, but never closing himself in a devotional world. Present day spiritual leaders seem to encourage people to bind themselves to such private devotional worlds both as an individual and as a particular community. They remain with fixed believes, ideas, perspectives and are somehow not ‘permitted’ to dare for an encounter with a different idea, belief or perspective. Attempting that

would be seen as being dishonest with their own devotional patterns. In fact, only in such encounters they get a context of modification and correction if needed.

One loses oneself by submerging oneself into some given patterns of practices within a closed devotional world. What do these private devotional worlds have to offer to the struggles and conflicts of the generation of today? Do these devotions have rooms to place these struggles? They do not formulate constructive symbols to involve the lives of this generation, instead, suggest myths and symbols that do not encounter their lives. As a result, their life and devotion/spirituality go in diverse paths and that in itself remains a conflict within; a spirituality or devotional life one follows which does not know the real concerns of one's life.

Instead of a formulation of meaningful devotion, the closed private devotional world takes up a moralising (and often condemning) mode to meet the issues. Practices and customs become something meaningful and fruitful only when one can find oneself in a life path. Devotional worlds remain external to oneself seemingly offering some comfort and consolation whereby one nails oneself to beliefs and practices that makes oneself in line with the devotional world. Many of the empty and sterile forms of devotional practices simply deny reality whether it be personal realities of oneself, of the community, or social or cultural phenomena. Instead they tend to promote self-righteousness and condemn others.

They learn to be happy in a comfort within the smoky shades which they learned to call as piety. It is really alarming about a generation when they are deeply interested in religious activities and pious practices, but are struck down

when faced with a struggle whether spiritual, emotional, or social. In fact, people in a devotional world encourages to deny or neglect the real conflicts. Having Christ in our hearts, we are to walk through the struggles and conflicts, with truth and humility, and courage and compassion. Christ should be there as the interior strength instead of being an ideal, principle, or an object of devotional practice.

We need to be enabled to understand the truth within the struggles and conflicts and dialogue with them. The symbols and myths within devotions that become easy solutions, interpretations, and part of religious imaginations do not provide such apt realisation or proper understanding. Conflicts and challenges are not something that should be denied or neglected. They are the real crosses that are to be embraced with responsibility. Only there we can find Christian hope, and offer Christian hope to the world.

Real devotions would seek truth of the living situations, and might reformulate practices that can bring transformation in our attitudes and responses. It is very crucial to reflect whether our devotional practices and religious imaginations (the way we imagine about God, heaven, blessing, life...) intent to make a Christ-formation happen in our person and communities, or, rather, we simply look for pleasing God expect favours for our private world. The answer may show why people are often in a 'worry and hurry' within devotional practices; which novena/Bible verse to be said for 'this particular purpose, which saint to be prayed to, which Our Lady to be visited, how much money to be given in donation, how many masses I must offer... They are found within their devotional bubble-world which are not devotions at all. To safeguard one's own devotional wall itself becomes a serious

concern. It does bring about an absence of Christ-presence and so a timely Christian presence.

Perhaps it is in one's helplessness one seeks any ways to get out of it. Sometimes this helplessness is seen being exploited. For some, creation of a devotional world is an easy shelter to escape from commitments. Life demands commitment to oneself to understand one's own life and its struggles, and similarly about one's community and the society at large. Since one is 'busy' with pious duties (which are thought to be the only works of God) one also excuses oneself from interactions in social responsibilities.

Today we may be influenced by the media and corporate world where performance is very much important. What God asks of us is not a perfect performance, but a responsible belonging. It is that relationship that heals, strengthens and gives us growth. If we can bring the very life of 'ours' with all its stress, uncertainties, and challenges, we will find grace meeting these situations. It is easy to create a devotional world, because it is about performance. But a pious and loyal heart cannot limit to performances. It does not see the need for worried doings to please God, ensure protection, cause blessings etc, because it has known Christ. Though it takes up crosses it has hope – devotion is to be the reflection of that relationship and hope.